

The Role of English in International Communication

Jumayeva Sevara Nizomiddinovna

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, 2nd year student

jumayevasevara411@gmail.com

+998 91 815 51 64

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Abstract: In today's society, English has been expressed as the global language among the speakers of thousands of different languages. The present paper emphasizes the information that English language is used as a prevalent and dominant language in order to maintain international relationships in many fields such as travel and tourism, education, press and media, entertainment fields, Internet communication and health fields.

Keywords: communication, lingua franca, globalization, travel, tourism, education, press and media, Internet communication, health fields.

Introduction

With the constantly growing levels of globalization and interconnectivity around the world, the importance of existing and appropriate ways of communication has been growing very rapidly in this world. It is an obvious fact that there has been always a need for a common language to interact with the present growing commerce and trade between companies from all over the world. As it is not a children play to be organized and verifiable about language, most people around the world are talking with the people of other regions in only one officially recognized language, that is, English. So nowadays everyone needs to know this language in order not to be behind some kind of international relationships like businesses, trades, educational fields and etc.

From these facts about English, it is not difficult to know that English is the language that has already used to be the first global lingua franca. The word lingua franca refers to a language which is used as a common means of communication between people of different languages and serves as a language mostly in trade, diplomacy, mass entertainment or cultural exchange. Unfortunately, English has become the fastest increasing language in our contemporary world.

Main part

Everyone knows that English has an official and specific status in nearly 70 countries. By mentioning these facts, one can easily understand that English is acquired such a vital role

as international language. Although about 375 million people speak it as a first language, more than 750 million people speak it as a second language. There are several reasons why so many people choose this language to speak. As we mentioned, many scientific or any kind of popular fields require to have knowledge of English. Therefore, it has been the first language for a majority of the population in different countries like United Kingdom, the United States, Australia and etc. Because most of the scientific branches and fields related to the business are fully developed in these countries for being English as their first language. In our country also English is taught in all schools by obeying the curriculum system from the first grade until graduation. And most of the pupils want to learn English hardly outside of school in order to study abroad. They were not only limited with school's knowledge. Since English occupied such a crucial position, many researchers have aimed to describe the term by evaluating the several aspects of the English. Among them, Ahulu coins it "General English", whereas David Crystal invents a phrase "English as a global language" and Jenkins coined another phrase, "English as an International Language". We can see the most widely used terms are English as a global language or lingua franca.

Globalization has also become a major cause for being English international. Because several factors contribute to English's global dominance like economic influence, technology and media, education and etc. So it has been judged as an commercial phenomenon by including more cooperation of global economic systems through the improvement of the commerce, press and media, education and especially travel and tourism. One scientist, Giddens mentions, "Globalization is a separation of space and time, with instantaneous communications, knowledge and culture could be shared around the world simultaneously". And we can consider the varied branches with that the English language has many connections and how they are related to them.

Travel and tourism

In these times, variety types of tourism have successfully developed in many countries and their population is predominantly used from English language in order to set up modern relationships with some travel or tourism agencies and departments. For example, cultural tourism is a type of travel that concentrated on exploring and appreciating the history, traditions, and the practices of different countries. If you want to work or set up business in cultural tourism, you are required to know and speak on it well. Moreover, if you have an ambition to travel abroad there is always need to know English to speak because in these countries, this language has recognized as their first or second language. And you do not have a choice to communicate in your own or other language which you know well. Undoubtedly, it is a formal language not only for departments, but also for tourists. Many international travel organizations propose new vacancies to people who can communicate well with tourists. So if you have to start your own business in mass tourism or work in this branch, there is also necessary to be aware of English. It is need to say that if you will work on this, you will have an opportunity to earn much more money than other professions salary.

Education

Presently, English has become the language that is increasingly used in the significant branches of education system. It is the medium of a great deal of the world's knowledge, especially in such areas like science and technology. Nowadays many students who go to foreign countries in order to boost their knowledge or get a higher education in some prestigious universities should have a knowledge of English. Because their education system are all organized in English. That's why now more and more students decided to learn English in order to study abroad like America, US, Australia and Canada. Since 1960s, English has become the typical medium of direction in higher education for some countries. For example, some innovative courses in Netherlands are extensively taught in English. Furthermore, learning universal communication language and its literature will provide us with logical principles for growing our critical or analytical thinking and practical skills. And these capabilities are highly assessed by employers over a number of industries so dominating English skills will open doors to numerous options.

Press and media

As other fields, the press and media also utilize from the English language in order to develop and improve their field. Nowadays about 60% of all widespread newspapers and magazines are printed in English. Furthermore, most of the programmes and broadcasts that we usually watch on TV are in English. Not only in our country, but also in other countries that was the English as their second language are common to print in English and it definitely helps to people who want to learn language themselves online. For example, by watching some broadcasts, interviews, cartoons, comics or films they can learn easily this language. Even now we can find many television channels which helps to learners to improve language skills especially speaking. By watching these channels in English, they can not only improve their speaking, but also they can increase vocabulary level by degrees. Besides that reading international articles and thesis in international journals would be beneficial for widening their reading skill because even when learning other languages, the more a person reads, the faster they will achieve the results they want. There is a substantial effect than other type of learning English because people can acquire it at home without going to any courses by spending money. And thus the press and media industry will benefit greatly from the English language than others.

Entertainment fields

The English is really fascinating language. From year to year, this powerful and lyrical language has been dominated in many popular fields. By studying the English language in the circumstances of music, TV and films, people can learn many useful things that need them in daily lives. For example, music is completely mentioned as a universal language, and currently songs that we can hear on the phone or the radio are mostly in English. It has a one cause that English is easier language many others because it does not have some uncomplicated words, specific vowels in spite of their grammatical difficulties. So it is

simpler to write expressive and interesting lyrics. This can be also one advantage of this language. Additionally, from the cinematic side, we know that world-famous movies are considered to be Hollywood movies and they are mainly in English. The extensive use of English in these forms of entertainment has donated to its international impact.

Internet communication

The 21st century is admitted as the age of information technology that links modern human life to the Internet. Using from social network are reflected to the current vocabulary that would be clear to all. And English language would be the solution to this. If we need something new information for our study or some other branches, information are provided in English deeply than our own language. And if you know this language well, it would be one of the little achievement for you. Besides that, by using from social media we can be aware of some important foreign news which presented in English. One example would be the coronavirus pandemic which we faced in 2020. It means that if we do not have any kind of social networks, we could with this dangerous pandemic.

Health fields

As English is an international language for technology, travel, press and media, it also plays an essential role in medicine. Proficiency in English is important for professionals in all fields, including medicine, to stay combative and well-informed in a fast-changing global environment. Because all doctors need to be skilled to read some foreign medical reports and research papers. Moreover, they should attend some medical conferences which presented in countries that highly developed regarding field of medicine in order to take experience and boost their knowledge on this. I think no matter how much they study and work on themselves, it is not enough because treating patients is one of the most complex tasks. Furthermore, the calling of many drugs, medicines, procedures and their instructions are related to the English. In order to comprehend them, medical professionals need to know this language.

Conclusion

In conclusion, there is need to say that English has already been a language which can be a part of something basics in various spheres like in social media, travel and tourism, entertainment fields and etc. Learning this language can give us more and more opportunities as well as we are living in a developed country. Its widespread use across diverse fields significantly highlights its role as a global lingua franca. The ability to communicate in English not only encourages smoother interactions between different cultures but also opens doors to circumstances for collaboration. Although learning this language seem to be difficult, by its chances people can build a more inclusive and interconnected group in international communication. We are completely sure about that English plays such a principal role around the world.

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